

CHARACTERISTICS OF INCREASING THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract: Nowadays, the share of working women at all stages of education is increasing, which is definitely the result of the reforms carried out by our state. This article discusses the theoretical aspects of increasing the role of women in improving the effectiveness of the educational process.

Key words: Educational stage, gender role, decree, stereotypes, comprehensive approach, educational institution, practical activity.

Introduction:

For many centuries, the woman was the guardian of the hearth, and everything related to the outside world was taken over by the man. This, of course, gave him the right to consider a woman far below him in status. But in the era of technological progress, scientific discoveries and feminism, the situation has changed radically. A woman in modern society has a completely different status and profession, she has other values and needs, forcing them to reconsider the views of the role of women in today's world.

To increase the socio-political activity of women in our country today, to create the necessary conditions for them to realize their abilities and opportunities in various fields and industries, to ensure that their rights and legal interests are unconditionally respected, Extensive work is being done to support motherhood and childhood, as well as to strengthen the institution of the family. In particular, Decree No. PF-5325 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2018 on "Measures to fundamentally improve activities in the field of supporting women and girls and strengthening the family institution" was announced¹. A number of works are being carried out on the basis of this Decree, including the work being carried out in the field of improving the effectiveness of women leaders in the educational process in educational institutions is commendable. In general, in Uzbekistan, important works of national importance are being carried out in order to strengthen the place and status of women in society.

Also, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-81 of March 1, 2022 "On measures to improve the system of working with the family and women, supporting the neighborhood and the clergy" established the institution of the family seven priority directions of the state policy on strengthening and supporting women, as well as the main tasks and directions of the committee's activities were defined².

¹ Decree No. PF-5325 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2018 "On measures to radically improve activities in the field of supporting women and strengthening the family institution".

² Decree No. PF-81 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 1, 2022 "On measures to improve the system of working with families and women, and supporting the neighborhood and clergy".

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-87 of March 7, 2022

"On measures to further accelerate work on systematic support of families and women"³ with the National program on increasing the activity of women in all aspects of the country's economic, political and social life in 2022-2026 and the National program on increasing the activity of women in all aspects of the country's economic, political and social life in 2022-2026 A comprehensive action plan aimed at implementation in 2022-2023 was approved.

The above decrees and decisions will certainly further strengthen the institution of the family, increase the socio-political activity of women, create conditions for the realization of their abilities and opportunities in various fields and sectors, and ensure that their rights and legal interests are unconditionally respected. campaign work on supporting motherhood and childhood in all aspects, increasing the influence and activity of women in society, encouraging their work, organizing, entrepreneurship, and business skills will be considered.

In modern society, a woman's role is no longer limited to doing housework, taking care of children, raising them, and serving her legal spouse. Now this position is considered outdated, and women who still choose it are considered adherents of conservative beliefs, who almost willingly enslave themselves to men. In fact, this approach is wrong in certain situations where a representative of the fairer gender sees his call to preserve family values and does not seek to separate his achievements from the successes of his spouse. After all, the symbol of personal ambition, career growth and the status of independence, at least financially, are not attractive to everyone today. Many women do not separate these criteria with their goals, preferring to fully serve the family. But here another extreme situation arises, because today the position of a woman in modern society is considered not only as a housewife, a faithful wife and a good mother. Often, girls' relatives and friends, first of all, their parents, from the teenage years, inspire that the main thing in life is not a strong family, but a stable social position. Therefore, before committing yourself to marriage, you must stand firm and become financially independent. Evidence on this issue is a warning that a woman should be prepared for this if suddenly her husband leaves the family, if the children are left without a father, if something else terrible happens. In fact, the position of a woman in modern society represents similar concerns, because today divorce is not considered a guilty or destructive thing. Thus, the probability of breaking the marriage bond is increasing every year: people are more strict and often do not want to put up with the slightest inconvenience in marriage.

As it turns out, a woman's role in the modern world is, first of all, success at work, career growth, financial independence, and only then the status of a wife and mother. Thus, the so-called revaluation of values occurs, which in turn leads to a reconsideration of the importance of family and marital relations in the life of the weaker sex.

Since the social role of women in modern society has changed radically in recent decades, the status of fair gender is also changing naturally. Thus, modern psychologists tend to consider the following main categories of women: managers, career holders, housewives, owners of liberal professions. In terms of character traits, leading women are similar to men in many ways: they are purposeful, believe in their abilities, and achieve everything

³ Decree No. PF-87 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of March 7, 2022 "On measures to further accelerate work on systematic support of families and women".

independently without relying on anyone's help. Self-realization is the main goal of career women who always put work first and achieve career success.

Studying the role of women in society is necessary for future specialists, who are called to be actively involved in solving large-scale social problems at the general and individual, private level. The acquired knowledge helps to form not only professional, but also moral qualities of students.

Many researchers say that a man becomes a man, and a woman becomes a woman in the process of adopting the appropriate roles accepted in a given society. However, it would be ridiculous to believe that the role is only a social norm embedded in the mind of the individual. To a large extent, this is determined by the motives of unconscious behavior, which are different in men and women.

In modern society, which is constantly changing in the field of society and culture, the "woman's question" has become extremely relevant: the position of a woman increasingly depends on the situation in society, on how quickly and successfully the reform of the legal aspects of life and the social-cultural reform of the institution of the family are carried out. the development of secular principles within.

Globalization and social saturation, dynamism and, most importantly, modern trends in the social and cultural development of society, characterized by the formation of a new status of a woman that meets the requirements of society, gave an opportunity to evaluate her role in society in a different way. The family-institution is very conservative, relatively few changes occur in it.

Today, it is known that a woman has a great role in achieving efficiency in the educational process. Since men and women perceive the world differently, their scientific discoveries reflect different perceptions of reality, and this means that there are effective features of taking into account specific feminine qualities.

Specific characteristics of increasing the role of women in increasing the effectiveness of the educational process are the most common stereotypes in the last 3 years:

- women are more adapted to mental and physical work than men (63.2%);
- self-awareness and personal growth of a modern woman is completely dependent on her career advancement (50.4%);
- the social role of a modern woman is reduced more to professional self-awareness than to family role positions (30.8%);
- career growth and material stability prevail in the value hierarchy of a modern woman (10.5%);
- modern woman appreciates freedom of rights and obligations (10%) .

Conclusion:

Thus, in educational processes, we see the quantitative superiority of women's social characteristics over individual characteristics, and the first places in the answers are those belonging to the specified type of roles.

References:

1.Decree No. PF-5325 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2018 "On measures to fundamentally improve activities in the field of supporting women and strengthening the family institution".

2. Decree No. PF-81 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 1, 2022 "On measures to improve the system of working with families and women, and supporting the neighborhood and clergy".
3. Decree No. PF-87 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 7, 2022 "On measures to further accelerate work on the systematic support of families and women".
4. Abdurauf Fitrat. Family or family management procedures. - Tashkent: Cholpon, 2019.
5. Information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2019. // www.stat.uz
6. Zherebkina I. A. Introduction to gender studies. – St. Petersburg: 2001